

Transformer asset–management using influence diagrams with Bayesian statistical models

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Abstract—Transformer health index (HI) is very useful for representing the overall health of a power transformer, due to the fact that it quantifies equipment condition based on different criteria that are related to the long-term degradation factors that cumulatively lead to the asset’s end-of-life. Moreover, transformer HI is a very powerful tool for managing assets and identifying future investment needs, as well as prioritizing present capital allocations and asset maintenance programs. This paper presents a novel approach to the transformer asset management, which leverages a combination of Bayesian statistical model for transformer HI analysis and influence diagrams. Influence diagrams, as extensions of the Bayesian networks, offer transparent decision-making process under uncertainty, while accounting for transformer HI test reliability and maintenance costs. Asset–management using the proposed model will be demonstrated on a concrete transformer data.

Keywords—Transformer, Asset management, Health Index, Bayesian models, Influence diagrams, Machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Power transformer represents very valuable and expensive single piece of high-voltage equipment, which can comprise up to 60 % of total investments in the transformer (sub)station. Transformer manufacturers often define the anticipated life of power transformers to be 25 to 40 years. However, some transformers in service are now approaching this age, and a number have reached as many as 60 years old. Nonetheless, failure rates remain low, and there is little evidence that many are at, or near, the end-of-life [1]. On the other hand, an increasing demand for improved financial and technical performance has pushed most power utilities to assess the actual condition of their transformers, regardless of their age. Thus, in order to achieve the optimal balance among capital investments, asset maintenance costs, and operating performance, there is an increased need to provide economic and technical justifications for engineering decisions and capital replacement plans [1].

This is where the Health Index (HI) of the transformer can be of exceptional value. It represents a practical tool that combines the results of operating observations, field inspections, with site and laboratory testing, into an objective and quantitative index, providing the overall health of the asset. Tests used for determining HI value include measuring or monitoring of dissolved gases, oil and/or conductor temperature, moisture content, oil quality (dielectric strength, acidity and color), partial discharges as well as frequency

response analysis, recovery voltage method, thermal imaging, tap changer tests, bushing tests, and other tests [2]–[7].

The main concern with a HI computation comes from the practical management of the numerous different criteria (and weighting factors associated with them) that are combined in different ways (using proprietary expert knowledge) to produce a HI value—as a composite of different effects condensed down to a single number [8]–[11]. Based on the computed HI value, which is confined within a certain range, a total of five categories have been proposed for describing the transformer condition [1], [11]. However, the exact number of categories used for the HI values, along with the range and limits of each category, is somewhat controversial and needs further scrutiny. From the audit of the published transformer HI models (some considered closed and proprietary) it can be seen that authors have pursued several very different approaches: weighted combination of many different criteria [1], using the fuzzy logic [5], binary logistic regression [11], artificial neural networks (ANNs), of different types and architectures for regression and/or classification, [2], [4], [10], [12].

This paper proposes a novel Bayesian statistical model for transformer HI analysis, based on the multivariate ordered “probit” regression. A robust version of the ordered probit regression will be presented, as implemented in the Bayesian setting [13], [14]. This approach acknowledges the fact that HI is described using several categories and leverages (sometimes proprietary) expert knowledge in defining these categories, while preserving inherent ordering among the categories (without the need for the imposed distance measure between the categories). The Bayesian approach to the transformer HI analysis offers important advantage over machine learning (ML) models, that is manifested in the interpretability of the model parameters and its explanatory power. Where ANNs and other ML models represent “black box” models, Bayesian model is an interpretable “white box” model [13]. It further benefits from the ability of the Bayesian inference to quantize uncertainty of model parameters, as well as from its hierarchical multilevel structure which accounts for the repeat and imbalance data sampling.

Furthermore, transformer HI is a very powerful tool for managing assets and identifying investment needs as well as prioritizing investments in capital and maintenance programs. Several studies have examined different power transformer condition assessment and life–management techniques, e.g., [9], [15], [16]. Many of these use transformer HI values

[1], [3], [7], while some use transformer outage data [17]. Asset-management techniques employ different models, e.g., Markovian model [18], simple Bayesian model [19], Bayesian networks model [20], models based on multi-parameters [3], and traditional techno-economic analysis [21].

This paper proposes a novel transformer asset-management technique that utilizes versatile “influence diagrams,” which are generalization of the Bayesian networks (i.e. probabilistic directed acyclic graphical models), for decision making based on the expected utility hypothesis [22], [23]. Influence diagrams offer transparent and natural decision-making process under uncertainty. A user-defined utility function, which here stipulates projected asset replacement and maintenance costs, features prominently in the proposed method, along with the estimated reliability of the transformer HI values for representing actual state of its health. Solving a decision problem amounts to determining an (optimal) strategy that maximizes the expected utility for the decision maker, and computing the expected utility of adhering to this strategy [22].

II. BAYESIAN STATISTICAL MODEL OF TRANSFORMER HEALTH INDEX

It is assumed here that there are multiple metric predictors (x_{ji}) for transformer health analysis and a total of K categories of the ordinal predicted variable. A linear combination of predictors is considered for computing HI, as is usually the case [11], although more complex interactions could be added (with a drawback of reduced model interpretability). Transformer HI values, as an ordinal predicted variable, are scored on the scale from 1 to 5 (without imposing distance measure between categories) and arranged as follows [5]: 1–Very bad (VB); 2–Bad (B); 3–Moderate (M); 4–Good (G); 5–Very good (VG).

Following a general description of the multivariate Bayesian ordinal (i.e. ordered) “probit” regression [13], [14], probability of outcome k for its robust version can be stated as follows:

$$p(y = k|\mu, \sigma, \{\theta_j\}) = \mathcal{T}_\nu \left(\frac{\theta_k - \mu}{\sigma} \right) - \mathcal{T}_\nu \left(\frac{\theta_{k-1} - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\mu = \beta_0 + \sum_j \beta_j \cdot x_{j,i} \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{T}_ν is a cumulative distribution function of the standard Student’s t distribution with ν degrees of freedom, and stands for the cumulative link function of the model. Eq. (1) applies even to the least and greatest ordinal values if two “virtual” thresholds at $-\infty$ and $+\infty$ are appended. Thus, for the least ordinal value ($y = 1$), the probability is

$$p(y = 1|\mu, \sigma, \{\theta_j\}) = \mathcal{T}_\nu \left(\frac{\theta_1 - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \quad (3)$$

and for the greatest ordinal value, denoted $y = K$, the probability is

$$p(y = K|\mu, \sigma, \{\theta_j\}) = 1 - \mathcal{T}_\nu \left(\frac{\theta_{K-1} - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \quad (4)$$

In addition, without the loss of generality, two extreme thresholds (θ_1 and θ_{K-1}) are fixed to the meaningful values on the outcome scale, which implies that the estimates of the other parameters are with respect to these anchors [14].

The predictor values are standardized ($\beta_0 \Rightarrow \zeta_0, \beta_j \Rightarrow \zeta_j$) prior to the introduction to the model, in order to make the Markov Chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) sampling of the model numerically as efficient as possible [13], [14]. The standardized parameter values ζ_0 and ζ_j , after having been evaluated by the MCMC sampling, can be transformed back to the original scale using the following expressions [14]:

$$\beta_0 = \zeta_0 - \sum_j \frac{\zeta_j}{\sigma_{x_j}} \cdot \bar{x}_j \quad (5)$$

$$\beta_j = \frac{\zeta_j}{\sigma_{x_j}} \quad (6)$$

The likelihood function here is the *Categorical* distribution $y_i \sim \text{Categorical}(p)$. Hyper-parameters of the proposed model are given non-informative priors (on the scale of the normalized data), except for the ζ_j which is given weakly regularizing prior [14]:

$$\zeta_0 \sim \text{Normal}(\mu = (1 + K)/2, \tau = 1/K^2) \quad (7)$$

$$\zeta_j \sim \text{Normal}(\mu = 0, \tau = 1/K^2), \forall j \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma \sim \text{Uniform}(K/1000, 10K) \quad (9)$$

$$\nu \sim \text{Exponential}(\lambda = 1/30) \quad (10)$$

The predictions of the posterior probability of each outcome for the new test samples, $x_{j,i}^{new}$, is carried out using the MCMC chain. Namely, at each step of the MCMC chain, the predicted outcome probabilities $p(\gamma|\mu(x), \sigma, \{\theta_j\})$ are computed by using (1), (3), and (4), with

$$\mu(x) = \beta_0 + \sum_j \beta_j \cdot x_{j,i}^{new} \quad (11)$$

Then, from the full chain of credible posterior predicted outcome probabilities, a central tendency is computed (e.g. mode) and a 95 % HDI (highest density interval) value [14].

III. BAYESIAN INFLUENCE DIAGRAMS FOR TRANSFORMER ASSET MANAGEMENT

Bayesian decision problems can be represented by using graphical notation known as the influence diagrams, which extend directed graphical models (i.e. Bayesian networks) by adding decision nodes and utility nodes to the original random variables of the Bayes network. A Bayesian network is a probabilistic network for belief update, whereas an influence diagram is a probabilistic network for reasoning about decision making under uncertainty, [22]. Fig. 1 portrays an influence diagram constructed for the problem of transformer asset management.

The central point of the decision making process—that is based on the influence diagrams—is the construction of the appropriate utility function, which stipulates projected asset replacement and maintenance costs [13], [22]. The utility

Fig. 1. Influence diagram for transformer asset management.

function presented hereafter will be constructed on the basis of the analysis provided in the Appendix 7 of the CIGRÉ Brochure 248 [19], which may be consulted at this point for additional information. Two actions are possible concerning the presumed state of the transformer health [19]:

$$d = \begin{cases} 0 : \{\text{Do nothing, wait and see.}\} \\ 1 : \{\text{Do immediate factory inspection.}\} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Since the state of the transformer health (as indicated by its HI value) and the above defined actions are both discrete variables, the utility function can be presented using the table of discrete values. For the hereafter treated transformer analysis, a utility function $U(d, h)$ is given by the Table I.

TABLE I
UTILITY FUNCTION GIVEN AS A TABLE OF DISCRETE VALUES.

Action	Health Index (h)				
	VG	G	M	B	VB
d = 0	0	0	-10000	-100000	-200000
d = 1	-20000	-20000	-10000	20000	50000

The utility function associates actions with the incurred costs of those actions (expressed in some fiat currency), while taking into account the presumed state of the transformer health (using its HI value). This means that, for example, if a decision is taken on moving the transformer to the factory floor for the immediate inspection ($d = 1$) and it turns out that it was in the healthy (enough) condition, this action would have represented wasted money entirely (amount of which depends on the power company's circumstances). However, doing nothing ($d = 0$) for a healthy transformer does not incur any costs. On the other hand, doing nothing ($d = 0$) for a transformer which is in a (very) bad condition could result with very large costs (due to the unexpected transformer repair costs and additional surcharges associated with penalties for non-delivering energy to the customers). Taking preventive action on such a transformer is associated with the positive

utility function, considering the possibility of recovering the factory inspection costs, increased life time expectancy, and the reduced failure rate of the refurbished transformer. Hence, it can be seen that there is a clear relationship between different actions and their projected costs. However, action is predicated on the prior belief regarding the state of the transformer health. Also, the utility function, expressed as a table of discrete values, will be specific to the particular distribution or transmission company [19]. The optimal action, from the economic perspective, depends on these uncertainties and projected costs.

In terms of the Bayesian decision making process, a *prior* expected utility for taking an action is

$$EU(d) = \sum_h p(h) \cdot U(d, h) \quad (13)$$

where $p(h)$ stands for the prior probability regarding the state of the transformer health, which can be obtained as an averaged probability from the transformer HI analysis on the fleet of transformers in the company's portfolio (Section II), or it can be assumed (either as a non-committal vague prior or a very particular prior distribution, depending on the situation). Namely, prior encodes state of information before seeing the data, so using different priors allows exploring consequences of beginning with different information about the state of the transformer health. The optimal action at this point, without incorporating any knowledge of the actual state of the transformer health, would be obtained as

$$d^* = \text{argmax}\{EU(d = 0), EU(d = 1)\} \quad (14)$$

However, if a test on the transformer is performed in order to acquire the information on its health condition (Section IV), which is associated with its own cost (Fig. 1), then a statistical model from the Section II will provide a probability distribution associated with the transformer health index. Also, the reliability of the test can be incorporated into the decision making process, using the conditional distribution $p(s|h)$ associated with its appropriate conditional probability table [13]. The conditional probability table can be determined from the transformer HI analysis on the fleet of transformers (Section II) and will depend on the state of the transformers and the particular model used for the HI analysis. It can also be determined empirically, from the past experience with transformer testing and will be influenced by the power utility company practices. For the hereafter treated transformer analysis, the test reliability is defined by the Table II. It can be seen that the conditional probability, $p(s|h)$, is asymmetric, emphasizing the difficulty of separating bad from good transformers.

This also assumes that the final judgment regarding the test performance can be passed using one of the following three different statements:

$$s = \begin{cases} 0 : \{\text{Test indicates a good transformer.}\} \\ 1 : \{\text{Test is inconclusive.}\} \\ 2 : \{\text{Test indicates a bad transformer.}\} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

TABLE II
TRANSFORMER TEST RELIABILITY AS A CONDITIONAL PROBABILITY
TABLE.

HI	Test indicator		
	s = 0	s = 1	s = 2
VG	0.85	0.13	0.02
G	0.75	0.20	0.05
M	0.20	0.60	0.20
B	0.05	0.25	0.70
VB	0.02	0.18	0.80

Due to the uncertainties inherent in the transformer HI analysis (and ambiguity associated with the definition of a good and bad transformer), there is a certain (although small) probability that the HI test will indicate a good transformer condition ($s = 0$), when its actual condition is not good (which can be determined upon its detailed inspection on the factory floor). Health test indicator variable (s) is ascribed a value by examining the shape of the probability distribution $p(h)$ on the transformer HI, after performing the actual test(s).

The posterior distribution over the state of the transformer health, considering the test reliability, is given by:

$$p(h|s) = \frac{p(s|h) \cdot p(h)}{p(s)} \quad (16)$$

$$p(s) = \sum_h p(h) \cdot p(s|h) \quad (17)$$

Now, a *posterior* expected utility of performing an action d , with the incorporated test reliability, is

$$EU(d|s) = \sum_h p(h|s) \cdot U(h, d) \quad (18)$$

The expected profit, after taking the test, can be obtained as follows:

$$EP = \sum_s p(s) \cdot EU(d^*(s)|s) \quad (19)$$

where $EU(d^*(s)|s)$ is the posterior expected utility for the optimal actions, $d^*(s)$, for each given test outcome (s). The optimal action, for each test outcome, is that which has produced a *maximal posterior* expected utility.

The financial value of the test, i.e. the price (P) that should be paid for performing the test in order for it to be profitable, can be obtained as a difference between the expected profit and the *maximum prior* expected utility:

$$P = EP - \max\{EU(d = 0), EU(d = 1)\} \quad (20)$$

If the actual cost of the test is larger then the value obtained by (20), it is not seen as profitable or opportune taking it.

IV. TRANSFORMER ASSET-MANAGEMENT EXAMPLE

In this paper, following transformer parameters will be used as the input data: water content in the transformer oil in ppm (Water), total acidity of the oil in mgKOH/g (Acidity), dissolved combustible gases in ppm (TDCG), oil breakdown voltage in kV (DBV), dissipation factor in percent (DF), and 2-Furfuraldehyde content in mg/L (Furan). Actual transformer

data, which forms a basis for the presented analysis, can be found in [5], [11]. Model will be trained on the synthetic dataset of one hundred transformers that is produced from the original dataset using the “data augmentation” method, which here assumes alterations of the original parameter values by random additions or subtractions of a certain percentage of its standard deviation. A simple random split of the synthetic dataset is used for cross-validating model performance during its training phase [13]. The trained model is then tested using the original dataset of thirty transformers (as a validation set).

Testing of this particular model on the transformer dataset from [2], [5], [11] shows that it has a very good accuracy. Model occasionally misinterpreted transformers of the “moderate” class, which is associated with the highest ambiguity. This proves that the proposed model can essentially be effective with only six transformer features, and is able to learn to recognize HI category from a small and unbalanced dataset. For the reference, model presented by Jahromi et al. uses as many as sixteen different transformer parameters for the HI computation [1]. As a comparison, Zuo et al. reported about the same (or slightly worst) performance of their binary logistic regression model on the same dataset [11].

Fig. 2 portrays the prior distribution of the transformer HI values, $p(h)$, obtained by averaging the prior probabilities for the HI categories of the thirty transformers from the test dataset [2], [5].

With the prior distribution, $p(h)$, from Fig. 2 and the utility function, $U(d, h)$, defined by the Table I, the prior expected utility for taking different actions follows from (13) as $EU(d = 0) = -41670$ and $EU(d = 1) = -3330$. Furthermore, by incorporating the test reliability, defined by the Table II, with the above mentioned prior distribution of the transformer health index (Fig. 2), the posterior expected utility can be obtained from (18). At this point, two different particular transformers will be examined, termed transformers A and B. Input data for these transformers is taken from [5] and given in the Table III.

By feeding the input data for transformer A (measured

Fig. 2. Prior distribution of the transformer HI values.

TABLE III
TEST TRANSFORMER INPUT DATA.

	Water (ppm)	Acidity (mgKOH/g)	DBV (kV)	DF (%)	TDCG (ppm)	Furan (mg/L)	HI value
Transformer A	21.7	0.024	32.5	0.075	483	0.86	G
Transformer B	21.2	0.226	48.7	0.424	215	5.53	B

values of the six metric variables from Table III) into the Bayesian statistical model (Section II), it yields posterior probability distribution on the transformer HI values (i.e. posterior predictions of the probabilities of each outcome) that is graphically presented in Fig. 3. Doing the same procedure with the transformer B, the Bayesian statistical model yields posterior probability distribution on the transformer HI values graphically presented in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the Bayesian model predicts the correct transformer class in both cases.

Now, from the posterior distribution of HI values for the transformer A (Fig. 3) it can be seen that the “test indicates a good transformer,” with a high certainty ($s = 0$), for which the associated maximum posterior expected utility equals $EU(d^* = 0|s = 0) = -3649$, which means that the optimal action for this transformer would be to “do nothing, wait and see” ($d^* = 0$). At the same time, from the posterior distribution of HI values for the transformer B (Fig. 4), it can be seen that the “test indicates a bad transformer” ($s = 2$), again with a high certainty. In this situation, maximum posterior expected utility equals $EU(d^* = 1|s = 2) = 22553$, which means that the optimal action would be to “do immediate factory inspection” ($d^* = 1$). Also, it can be stated that in the case

that the “test is inconclusive,” optimal action would be to “do immediate factory inspection.” It has been found that the decision process is quite immune to the changes of the utility function, as long as they are reasonable and meaningful.

The expected profit from (19), assuming optimal action for each given test outcome, equals $EP = 3565$. The financial value attached to performing a test on the transformer is estimated from (20) at the level of $P = 6895$. This means that it would be cost-effective to do the test only in case its actual price is lower then or equal to this value.

Presented Bayesian model for the asset-management can be employed using the process of Bayesian updating [13], [14], which, as an iterative learning process, can be seen as particularly beneficial in the context of transformer maintenance with a continuous diagnosis. In this process, conclusions reached concerning the transformer health, after the test is taken, become the starting point for the future inference regarding its maintenance decisions. This means that the probability distribution from Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 can be, independently, introduced as a new prior probability and used with the same utility function for formulating new decisions at a later time. Hence, newly introduced (prior) information regarding

Fig. 3. Posterior distribution of the HI values for transformer A.

Fig. 4. Posterior distribution of the HI values for transformer B.

the health status of transformer A with ($s = 0$) identifies optimal action as “do nothing, wait and see” ($d^* = 0$), with a maximum posterior expected utility of ${}^{new}EU_A(d^* = 0|s = 0) = -598$. The expected profit in case of transformer A is estimated from (19) at the level of ${}^{new}EP_A = -1930$. At the same time, new information on transformer B with ($s = 2$) identifies optimal action as “do immediate factory inspection” ($d^* = 1$), with a maximal posterior expected utility of ${}^{new}EU_B(d^* = 1|s = 2) = 24032$. The expected profit in case of transformer B is estimated at the level of ${}^{new}EP_B = 22940$. The financial value of the test, from (20), for both transformers A and B, due to their very strongly informed prior distributions, is now approximately zero, indicating that the price of the test cannot be recovered and the optimal action in both cases should be taken without testing. The expected profit determined for different transformers, within the power utility company’s portfolio, can be used for prioritizing their maintenance schedules and selecting those units which would benefit the most from the early intervention (i.e. preventive factory inspection).

V. CONCLUSION

Transformer HI can be analyzed using classification or regression models. This paper proposed a particular type of Bayesian statistical model for estimating HI of transformers. It is a robust version of the multivariate Bayesian ordinal “probit” regression, a type of generalized linear model which falls under the “multiclass” classification domain. Regression algorithms, when applied to the HI analysis, often produce values outside the intended range. In addition, where different proposed models based on the “black box” machine learning algorithms lack interpretability, here proposed model is a “white box” model with interpretative predictive power and measurable uncertainty of its parameters. It has been shown that the here proposed model has about the same (or even higher) accuracy and predictive power than the previously presented models, with the added benefit of interpretability and quantized uncertainty of its parameters.

In addition, this paper proposed a novel asset–management technique for optimal transformer maintenance under uncertainty, which is based on the versatile influence diagrams. It features probabilistic uncertainty regarding the state of the transformer health, reliability of the test for the transformer HI analysis, and projected asset’s maintenance costs determined by the power utility company. Proposed decision making process, in essence, manages risk associated with taking different actions by leveraging uncertain information regarding the transformer health and the expected costs. In this way, each decision has a monetary value attached to it, which depends on the particular circumstances defined by the power utility company itself, allowing for the optimal decision to be identified.

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